

Development of 3D Printed Pharmaceutical Cocrystals

Version 1

Description

The project investigates the integration of pharmaceutical cocrystals into extrusion-based 3D printed solid dosage forms, aiming to improve the solubility, stability, and personalized delivery of drugs through tailored geometries and controlled release profiles. The research will generate experimental and computational datasets related to cocrystal screening and characterization (e.g., PXRD, DSC, TGA, FTIR, Raman), formulation and rheological properties, 3D printing process parameters, mechanical testing, dissolution and drug release studies, as well as simulation and structure–process–performance relationship data.

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all project data are systematically collected, well documented, securely stored, and appropriately shared. Data management will follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to support transparency, reproducibility, and Open Science, enabling reuse of datasets by other researchers and industry stakeholders working in pharmaceutical 3D printing and cocrystal-based dosage forms.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project No. Izp-2025/1-0263 "Development of 3D Printed Pharmaceutical Cocrystals" (project manager: Dr. chem. Artis Kons, 01.01.2026. - 31.12.2028., 300 000.00 EUR).

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Development of 3D Printed
Pharmaceutical Cocrystals

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Development of 3D Printed Pharmaceutical Cocrystals](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Development of 3D Printed Pharmaceutical Cocrystals](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Experimental and computational data on extrusion-based 3D printed pharmaceutical cocrystals](#)

This Description covers all research data generated in the project on 3D printed pharmaceutical cocrystals, including experimental measurements, 3D printing records, and computational outputs. It defines how these data are collected, documented, stored, and shared in line with FAIR principles to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and reuse by other researchers and industry.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data will be collected to design, optimize, and evaluate extrusion-based 3D printed pharmaceutical cocrystal dosage forms, directly supporting the project objectives of improving solubility, stability, and personalized drug delivery for poorly water-soluble APIs. Primary data will originate from laboratory experiments

(cocystal synthesis and characterization, formulation development, 3D printing trials, mechanical and dissolution testing) and from computational studies underpinning structure–process–performance relationships.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- XLS
- Others

XY

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Published crystallographic and literature data will be consulted, but the core project datasets will be newly generated.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful to researchers in pharmaceutical sciences, crystal engineering, materials science, and additive manufacturing who work on solid dosage forms, cocrystals, and 3D printing technologies. It may also be valuable for pharmaceutical and technology companies developing personalized medicines, 3D printed dosage forms, or modeling tools for structure–process–performance relationships.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

- DOI
- arXiv

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be available after the related scientific publication is released.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

ResearchGate Data

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data can be accessed using standard scientific software such as Microsoft Excel, Python, and common image analysis tools. These tools are widely used in research and support open or standard file formats.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

A CC BY license allows maximum re-use while ensuring proper attribution to the project and authors

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2038-12-31

Data will be preserved in stable repositories that commit to long-term archiving, with an intended reuse horizon of at least 10 years beyond the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs related to data storage, backup, curation, and open-access deposition (including possible publication fees) are covered from the project budget and institutional infrastructure resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Artis Kons (0000-0002-4055-8442)

The project leader is responsible for overall data management, while designated team members manage day-to-day tasks such as file organization, metadata entry, backups, and repository deposition.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Long-term data preservation will be ensured through open repositories such as Zenodo, which provides free access and long-term archiving of research data.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data security will be ensured through physical access control to laboratory facilities, password protection on all institutional computers, and the use of firewalls to protect the network from unauthorized access.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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